

Superhydrophobic Coatings For Enhanced Fiber Composite Materials

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Fabrication of superhydrophobic coatings on CF-PEEK, CF-Epoxy and CF-Nylon

- Reinforced fiber composites find extensive use in naval structures, sporting gear, aircraft components, modern automotive construction and biomedical parts
- Composite material are susceptible to moisture degradation impacting their mechanical and thermal properties
- Fabrication of micro-nano textured pattern on a substrate surface lead to Cassie Baxter state imparting superhydrophobicity and providing protection from moisture
- Polyurethane poly (methyl methacrylate) interpenetrating polymer network and FSiO₂ coatings were used to fabricate superhydrophobic fiber reinforced composites [1]
- Substrates coated with dewetting material showed reduced water absorption as compared to uncoated substrates

References:

[1] W. S. Y. Wong, Z. H. Stachurski, D. R. Nisbet, and A. Tricoli, "Ultra-durable and transparent self-cleaning surfaces by large-scale self-assembly of hierarchical interpenetrated polymer networks," ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces, vol. 8, no. 21, pp. 13615–13623, 2016.

Reduced water absorption for coated substrates

Micro-nano roughness and superhydrophobicity

Automated Superhydrophobic Fiber Reinforced Composite Fabrication

